

BIOCHEMISTRY OF *AEROBACTER AEROGENES* AND *BACILLUS CEREUS*.

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Dulcitol-negative *Aerobacter aerogenes* and dulcitol-positive *A. aerogenes* (Syn. *A. Oxytocum*) have been isolated from potatoes suffering from the black centre disease, and *B. cereus* from rotting 'Chiku' fruit (*Achras sapota*, L.). The products of metabolism of these three organisms on carbohydrate substrates have been examined. Acetyl methyl carbinol, ethyl alcohol, acids and gases are the principal products. The influence of the nature of substrate, hydrogen ion concentration of media, the temperature of fermentation and the effect of aeration have been studied in detail.

Although micro-organisms produce plant diseases of diverse types, the biochemistry of the organisms present on diseased plants has not been extensively studied. The present paper is a report of the investigation carried out in connection with two kinds of plant diseases. The first is a pathological condition typical with potatoes and is marked by the appearance of a dark spot or ring in the centre. The second disease is met with in the fruit 'chiku' (*Achras sapota*, L.) and results in extensive breakdown of the internal cell structure of the fruit. From diseased potatoes thirteen morphologically individual organisms were isolated which produced acetylmethyl carbinol and ethyl alcohol in varying amounts. Out of these two proved to be vigorous fermenters of starch and glucose with the formation of these products. These two have been subsequently identified as a new physiological strain of *Aerobacter aerogenes*. The two differ amongst themselves in that one of them is dulcitol-positive and the other is dulcitol-negative. From the 'chiku' fruit a bacillus identified as *B. cereus* has been isolated. Both *A. aerogenes* and *B. cereus* occur widely in soils and thereby find their way into the plant and probably participate with other organisms in causing the disease.*

* The authors are not yet in a position to state with certainty whether these two micro-organisms are the specific producers of the respective diseases in potatoes and 'chiku' fruit. They are, however, the predominant types present in the diseased tissue. Experiments are now in progress in which healthy potatoes and 'chiku' fruit will be inoculated with vigorous cultures of the *A. aerogenes* and *B. cereus* strains, in order to test if the characteristic symptoms of the two diseases can thereby be reproduced.

On a reference to literature a few observations on the metabolic products of *A. aerogenes* were found (*cf.* Harden and Walpole, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1906, **B**, 77, 399; Walpole, *ibid.*, 1911, **B**, 83, 272; Neuberg, Nord and Wolff, *Biochem. Z.*, 1920, **112**, 144; Fred and Peterson, *J. Infect. Dis.*, 1920, **27**, 539; Nagai, *Biochem. Z.*, 1923, **141**, 261; Levy-Bruhl, Cado and Huri, *Ann. Inst. Pasteur*, 1931, **58**, 498) but none in case of *B. cereus*. Even with *A. aerogenes* no systematic study has been described. Furthermore, the two strains of *A. aerogenes*, isolated by the authors from potatoes, differ from the usual types in that they do not cause a rapid evolution of gas and acid from lactose and hence they are physiologically different from the known strain. A detailed study of their metabolic products under different conditions of substrate and nutrition, temperature, hydrogen ion concentration, aeration, etc. would be interesting apart from the question of plant disease.

The isolation of the organisms was carried out as usual by scraping the diseased portion, shaking the scrapings in sterile water and plating and replating. The dilution method of isolation was resorted to and thirteen morphologically different organisms were isolated from the diseased potatoes. These individuals were regrown in nutrient agar slants adjusted to p_H 7.0 at 40°, when a vigorous growth was obtained. The pure cultures were maintained on nutrient agar slopes adjusted to p_H 7.0. Northrop, Ashe and Senior (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1919, **39**, 1) have isolated an acetone and ethyl alcohol-producing organism from old potatoes. In the earlier experiments, therefore, these two compounds were specially looked for in the metabolic products. Actually ethyl alcohol was found to be produced by all the three organisms but no acetone except in traces. On the other hand acetylmethyl carbinol was formed in practically all cases.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The preliminary experiments were carried out on a starch-peptone-calcium carbonate medium. Subsequently, however, glucose was used as the carbohydrate substrate along with various other nutrients as described under 'substrates and nutrition'. The media were contained in bottles or flasks which were sealed suitably after inoculation and incubated at the appropriate temperature for fifteen days, after which the contents were analysed.

Methods of Analysis.—For qualitative testing for the different alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, acids, etc. the usual reactions were employed. In

the quantitative analysis complication arose on account of the fact that both acetylmethyl carbinol and acetone give similar reactions with different reagents used in the analysis which depend upon the reactivity of the CH_3CO -group, present in both the cases. However, as found by Langlyke and Peterson (*Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1937, 9, 163) acetylmethyl carbinol distils over from an aqueous solution at a constant rate independent of its concentration. Thus the amounts that distilled over in the first 50 c.c. fraction and the second 25 c.c. fraction, when 100 c.c. were distilled, were 59.7% and 23.9% respectively of the original amount present in the liquid distilled. Acetone and ethyl alcohol on the other hand distilled over rapidly and quantitatively in the first 50 c.c. of the distillate. Acetylmethyl carbinol can thus be estimated by the iodoform method in the second 25 c.c. portion of the distillate and this amount multiplied by the factor 4.18, therefore, gives the total amount present in the original liquid. The portion of the first 50 c.c. of the distillate which was expected to contain all the ethyl alcohol and acetone and 59.7% of the total acetylmethyl carbinol was also analysed by the iodoform method and after making a slight correction for alcohol it was found that the amount of acetone present in most cases was negligible. Another portion of this first fraction of the distillate was oxidised with a known excess of potassium dichromate and from the amount of dichromate consumed the amount of ethyl alcohol present was calculated after allowing for the acetylmethyl carbinol.

The dulcitol-negative and the dulcitol-positive strains of *A. aerogenes* will be referred to as *A. aerogenes* I and *A. aerogenes* II respectively.

Effect of Substrate and Nutrition.—The following three media have been studied.

A. Glucose (5%), peptone (0.5%) and calcium carbonate (2%), p_{H} 7.0.

B. Glucose (5%), ammonium phosphate (0.5%), potassium dihydrogen phosphate (0.5%), potassium phosphate (0.01%) and magnesium sulphate (0.5%), p_{H} 7.0.

C. Glucose (5%), peptone (0.5%), meat extract (0.3%), sodium chloride (0.5%) and calcium carbonate (2%), p_{H} 7.0.

50 C.c. of the media after inoculation were incubated at 26° for 15 days after which the contents were analysed.

TABLE I.

Medium.	Expt. No.	% on weight of sugar fermented		Expt. No.	% on weight of sugar fermented		Expt. No.	% on weight of sugar fermented		
		Acetyl-methyl carbinol.	EtOH.		Acetyl-methyl carbinol.	EtOH.		Acetyl-methyl carbinol.	EtOH.	
		<i>A. aerogenes</i> I			<i>A. aerogenes</i> II			<i>B. cereus</i>		
A	1	2'15	14'58	1	2'16	16'66	1	4'29	0'89	
	2	1'97	14'27	2	2'23	16'81	2	4'03	1'38	
B	1	2'00	3'25	1	5'45	3'21	1	3'21	1'33	
C	1	2'06	11'14	1	1'58	9'17	1	4'40	3'15	

It is obvious that for the production of ethyl alcohol glucose-peptone-calcium carbonate medium is more suitable than the one containing glucose and inorganic salts, although quite heavy growths were obtained even with the latter. *A. aerogenes* II gave better yield of acetylmethyl carbinol in the glucose-inorganic salt medium than the glucose-peptone-calcium carbonate one.

Effect of Hydrogen Ion Concentration.—Acids were formed during fermentation in varying amounts by all the three organisms. *A. aerogenes* strains gave more acids than *B. cereus*. The study of the influence of p_H was carried out with two media.

(A) Glucose (5%), peptone (0.5%), calcium carbonate (2%).

(B) Glucose (5%), ammonium phosphate (0.5%); potassium dihydrogen phosphate (0.5%), magnesium sulphate (0.5%) and potassium phosphate (0.01%).

The incubation was carried out as usual in sealed bottles at 26°.

TABLE II.

50 C.c. medium in 500 c.c. sealed flask.

Organism.	Media.	pH.	Expt. No.	% on wt. of sugar fermented.		% of sugar fermented.	
				Acetylmethyl carbinol.	Ethyl alcohol.		
<i>A. aerogenes</i> I	A	7.0	1	2.12	14.47	66.0	
			2	1.69	15.04	60.6	
			7.4	1	1.97	14.27	63.5
			2	2.15	14.58	61.0	
			8.5	1	2.44	12.92	67.9
			2	2.46	11.54	69.5	
<i>A. aerogenes</i> II	A	7.0	1	2.26	15.04	79.1	
			2	2.60	15.85	80.5	
			7.4	1	2.10	16.66	68.0
			2	2.23	16.81	73.2	
			8.5	1	1.81	16.27	75.6
			2	2.43	17.03	77.0	
<i>B. cereus</i>	A	7.0	1	3.33	1.32	67.8	
			7.4	1	4.29	0.89	63.4
			2	4.03	1.38	65.4	
			1	2.53	0.76	73.0	
<i>A. aerogenes</i> I	B	6.2	1	8.20	3.88	100.0	
			7.0	1	1.70	3.19	100.0
			2	2.30	3.33	100.0	
			7.6	1	1.50	3.17	100.0
			2	1.11	2.97	100.0	
<i>A. aerogenes</i> II	B	6.2	1	8.43	3.51	100.0	
			7.9	1	5.41	3.20	100.0
			7.6	1	5.29	3.00	100.0
<i>B. cereus</i>	B	6.2	1	4.85	3.11	11.4	
			7.0	1	3.21	2.33	49.0
			7.6	1	2.91	1.72	32.8

Although it is difficult on account of the variable nature of the fermentations to draw accurate conclusions, yet it may broadly be stated that the optimum p_H for the production of acetylmethyl carbinol varies with the nature of the substrate. In case of glucose-peptone medium the optimum was on the whole on the alkaline side, *i.e.*, p_H 7.5-8.5, whilst in the medium with inorganic nitrogen source, it was on the acidic side. *i.e.*, at p_H 6.2. The same general conclusions were drawn when 50 c.c. of the medium were fermented in 250 c.c. or 500 c.c. sealed flasks, *i.e.*, with larger volume of air.

Effect of Temperature.—The medium contained glucose, peptone and calcium carbonate. 50 C.c. of the medium were fermented in 250 c.c. sealed flasks.

TABLE III.

Organism.	Temp.	Expt. No.	% on wt. of sugar fermented.		% of sugar fermented.
			Acetylmethyl carbinol.	Ethyl alcohol.	
<i>A. aerogenes</i> I	26°	1	1.97	14.27	61.5
		2	2.15	14.58	61.5
	33	1	1.95	9.95	100.0
		2	1.70	12.96	100.0
	40	1	6.11	10.36	100.0
	<i>A. aerogenes</i> II	26	1	2.10	16.66
2			2.23	16.81	68.1
33		1	2.58	11.13	100.0
		2	3.01	10.47	100.0
40		1	3.69	9.81	100.0
		2	4.11	9.63	100.0
<i>B. cereus</i>	26	1	4.29	0.89	31.8
		2	4.13	1.38	32.7
	33	1	2.99	3.55	68.1
	40	1	6.96	3.26	83.4

The requirements of temperature for acetylmethyl carbinol production and ethyl alcohol production are inversely related to each other for *A. aerogenes*. Acetylmethyl carbinol is formed in largest amount at 40°, at which temperature alcohol production is minimum. The inverse is the case at 26°. For *B. cereus* the optimum temperature for acetylmethyl carbinol

formation is again 40° but for alcohol production it is 33°. These results have been confirmed in a second series of experiments in which the fermentation was carried out in contact with larger volume of air, i.e., 50 c.c. fermented in 500 c.c. flasks.

TABLE IV.

Effect of aeration.

The media used consisted of glucose (5%), peptone (0.5%), calcium carbonate (2%), p_H 7.0.

Organism.	Expt. No.	Temp. of incubation.	% of sugar fermented			
			50 C.c. media in 250 c.c. flasks.		50 C.c. media in 500 c.c. flasks.	
			Acetyl-methyl carbinol.	Ethyl alcohol	Acetyl-methyl carbinol.	Ethyl alcohol.
<i>A. aerogenes</i> I	1	26°	1.97	14.27	3.47	13.82
	2		2.19	14.58	—	—
<i>A. aerogenes</i> II	1	26	2.10	16.66	3.01	—
	2		2.23	16.81	3.37	13.12
<i>B. cereus</i>	1	26	4.29	0.89	13.41	2.78
	2		4.03	1.38	—	—
<i>A. aerogenes</i> I	1	33	1.95	11.45	2.94	—
	2		1.70	—	2.28	11.34
<i>A. aerogenes</i> II	1	33	2.58	11.13	2.69	11.44
	2		3.01	10.47	—	—
<i>B. cereus</i>	1	33	2.87	3.66	4.82	4.20
	2		3.09	4.10	—	—

Production of acetylmethyl carbinol is, therefore, favoured by increased aeration with all the three organisms at the two temperatures studied. This supports the findings of Walpole (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1911, **B**, 83, 272) and Kluver, Donker and Hooft (*Proc. Acad. Sci. Amsterdam*, 1925, 28, 317), who have found that with *B. lactis aerogenes* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* respectively the yield of acetylmethyl carbinol is increased by aeration and by the addition of hydrogen acceptors such as

methylene blue. No regular effect of aeration on ethyl alcohol production can be noticed from the above data.

Further detailed work is being carried out on the biochemistry and metabolic products of *B. cereus* and will be reported in due course.

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